

Cyber-physical security in the Water Sector

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Abstract

Water utilities serve essential societal needs while their services might be utilised in other critical sectors (e.g., in the production of energy) and a halting of operations would have a serious societal and economic impact.

Traditionally, cyber and physical security have been conceived and managed as two separate entities. Water critical infrastructures have always given more attention to physical than cyber security. However, current sophisticated attacks are disrupting both virtual and physical network elements, giving rise to a wide number of vulnerabilities and complex cyber-physical attacks with potential disastrous consequences.

In addition, today's operating needs have created a technology convergence of physical and cyber infrastructures. Automation has increased due to the need to improve operational efficiencies and workforce shortages. While these changes improve water system operability, they have also created serious vulnerabilities because there has not been a concurrent improvement in the security defence mechanisms. As today's ICS has become IT-centric and highly connected due to the introduction of secondary networks (e.g., the Internet of Things – IoT), the water sector is exposed to the same cybersecurity threats as the IT system, but without appropriate solutions.

Furthermore, one of the major challenges the Water sector faces is the lack of cybersecurity situational awareness and the gaps in defines in depth mechanisms. The common believe in many sectors is that a high level of security can be achieved by deploying cutting edge technologies to protect and counter potential risks. However, the truth is that defence in depth can never be achieved if organizations do not clearly understand the relationship of vulnerabilities, threats and the mitigation measures used to protect the operations, personnel, and technologies of an ICS. Defence-in-depth is a holistic approach that considers the interconnections and dependencies among the aforementioned entities while protecting the organization's assets and using their available resources to provide effective layers of monitoring and protection based on the business's exposure to cybersecurity risks.

1. The Water sector as a Cyber-physical-social system

Cyber-physical-social systems (CPSSs) [1] represent a type of system that integrates cyber, physical, and social components to enable new functionalities and services [2]. These systems are designed to be adaptive, responsive, and intelligent, allowing them to sense, learn, and interact with their environment and users. CPSSs are characterized by their ability to collect, process, and analyse large amounts of data from different sources, including sensors, social media, and online platforms. They can also actuate physical processes, such as controlling traffic lights or adjusting the temperature in a building, based on the information they gather. CPSSs have wide-ranging applications, from smart cities and transportation systems to healthcare and education and are expected to play an increasingly important role in shaping our lives and society.

A CPSS for a water system comprises three interconnected components: Physical Space, Cyber Space, and Social Space. The Physical Space includes the physical infrastructure and assets of the system. The Cyber Space includes the digital components, such as sensors and management systems, which are integrated into the water system architecture. The Social Space comprises the stakeholders who are engaged in the water system design, including end-users, regulators, policymakers, and other members of the community. The intersections between the three spaces show the interdependence and integration between them, highlighting the need for a comprehensive approach to the design, management, and security of digital water systems.

2. The Challenges

The nature of the water sector has led to a slower process of digitalization compared to other critical infrastructure sectors, which is also due to a list of security challenges limiting the modernization of the water sector. In the following sections an overview of the primary challenges of the sector as resulted from the analysis of the STOP-IT project is provided.

Limited Integration Between Physical Security and Cybersecurity

Even though the infrastructures of the water sector comprise interconnected physical and cyber assets, physical security and cybersecurity remain fragmented.

The process of digital transformation increases the interaction and connection between the two layers, the cyber and the physical, thus the water systems are evolving into cyber-physical systems in which physical processes and assets are integrated with computational engineered systems.

Although safety has been high priority in the water sector for years and cybersecurity is becoming of higher concern, still measures and approaches that consider a global integrated security context, physical and cyber, are missing and therefore leading to the inability to cope with combined cyber-physical attacks which are of major concern. In fact, the real risk rises when a cyber-attack puts in danger the service provided, meaning when a cyber-attack can develop into a service disruption, e.g., contamination, unsupplied water, discharge of pollutants, etc... meaning, cyber security has to be about an integrated cyber-physical approach for risk management linking security and safety and in which the cyber and the physical layers of the water systems are secured as an integrated cyber-physical domain.

Furthermore, risk management practices should investigate scenarios exploiting combined physical and cyber threats in the context of cascading attacks, since they are the most complex risk events to be prepared for.

Willingness to share information on threats to cybersecurity

The water sector lacks collective situational awareness of cyber threats. This is because water utilities and associated IT service providers do not systematically share information on experienced cyber-attack events which could help to further assess the state of cybersecurity in the water sector, increase preparedness and the ability to protect the service. Being aware of security incidents that have occurred is very important for understanding and prepare for the risks that might happen.

Sharing of information about threats to cybersecurity and the development of procedures to exchange best practices among operators, not limited to the water sector, but also across critical entities, are considered of major relevance to faster the ability to react in case of cybersecurity incidents.

Digital and cybersecurity culture maturity

Developing proper prevention and response strategies requires not only implementing technical security measures, but also establishing a cybersecurity culture, through competence building, awareness creation and communication. There is currently a gap in digital knowledge in general and specifically in cybersecurity in the water sector. The knowledge gaps are both potential sources of risks and barriers for the process of digitalization. They are sources of risk, since about 90 percent of attacks appears to be caused by human error and, in a sort of downward spiral, limited competence creates concerns about security, which represent barrier and disincentive to boosting digitalization of the sector.

Therefore, the human sphere is a fundamental pillar, together with technologies and physical protection towards the service cyber protection and as such it is essential to increase cybersecurity awareness, education, training and best practices within the water industry.

Risk for supply chain attacks

To this day, research has been focusing on protecting water infrastructures against cyber-physical attacks and threats. While it is vital to protect water infrastructures, to best of our knowledge, no one has looked at the (technical and operational) risks of integrating digital solutions with water utilities. This is partially because such solutions are usually not connected to the water utilities directly, but also because there is a race to market, and security is not a priority.

Therefore, there is a need to provide security recommendations to be adopted by digital solution providers and water utilities on how to securely develop and integrate solutions in water utilities' systems, also as (but not limited) a valuable instrument supporting the accomplishment of the NIS2 directives stressing the need to address cybersecurity along the entire supply chain.

3. Gaps

To address the above-listed challenges there is need for developing, adopting and deploying novel CIP solutions for the critical infrastructures of the finance sector. Specifically, the following solution guidelines are envisaged:

Based on the weaknesses of the sector, the following best practices and recommendations are derived to improve cybersecurity in the water sector and across critical entities [3]:

- Addressing both physical & cyber risk creates a more comprehensive framework for sectors such as the water & wastewater sector.
- The scope of information sharing between different critical entities in Europe should be further expanded to effectively encourage cooperation and communication.
- Need to increase the efforts on raising awareness in cybersecurity across the various EU critical sectors, including the water sector.

- Utilise the benefit of adopting risk management approaches and solutions developed in recent EU funded research projects by H2020 (e.g., from INFRA, Critical Infrastructure Protection - CIP calls) and other programmes to overcome some of the implementation challenges of the proposed Critical Entities Resilience (CER) Directive and the NIS-2.
- Promote training activities for water operators at different decision level for an effective and adequate response; training should be based on core courses, augmented by a training programme involving discussion and operational exercises based on realistic and plausible scenarios.

In the terms of policy implications, the recommendations are (see also [3]):

- Authorities should strive for collaborative tools to share information and to create collective situational awareness of cyber threats.
- Create competence development programmes on cyber security in the water sector.
- Support initiatives, as an EU Water ISAC, as secure environment for information and best practice sharing, as well as for training initiatives and activities.

4. The technologies helping to overcome the gaps in the water sector

Progress regarding the uptake of digital solutions by utilities has been hindered by a perceived risk of lack of security. This is a risk that can be minimised through the use of appropriate technologies and tools to secure the Digital Water Systems; although such security tools that integrate cyber-physical risk approaches exist and have been tested (as in STOP-IT), they have not yet been broadly accepted by the water sector. The implementation of those solutions should be supported.

The research outcomes of the STOP-IT project provide an example of working towards a more comprehensive approach in enhancing the resilience of critical entities in the water sector. The STOP-IT consortium has collaborated in different directions: raising awareness about cybersecurity in the water sector in 6 countries, by organising dedicated thematic communities of practice in the 8 water utilities (Deliverables D2.1 and D2.2¹); supporting water utilities to systematically protect their systems by addressing cyber-physical security as an integrated approach for risk management through the use of the developed stress-testing platform (D4.2 and D4.4) and by developing up to 30 technological solutions for physical, IT and SCADA protection at least at Technology Readiness Level - TRL 7². All the solutions can be integrated through the ensured interoperability or used as standalone (D6.7 and D6.8) - <https://stop-it-project.eu/results-and-downloads/tools-technologies/>; and improving the ability to cope with new risks, by building competence through training activities (D8.1, D8.2, D8.3 and <https://stop-it-project.eu/results-and-downloads/transfer-training-activities/>).

The Digital Water City project (DWC) aimed at creating digital solutions to link water management in the physical world to the digital spheres such as sensor networks, real-time monitoring, machine learning, etc., ensuring security.

In the context of security, the main outcome of the project is the risk management guide³, which embeds the results and experience gained in the project and provides an overall document supporting the adoption of a risk management process against cyber threats at strategic, tactical and operational

¹ Please consult project website to see the deliverables.

² https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/7998574>

level. The aim of the guide is to support water organisations in the implementation of a complete risk management process in order to increase the preparedness against potential cyber and/or physical threats connected to the digital solutions adopted. In addition, a series of security recommendations and best practices for technology providers are described. Two digital solutions served as use cases to test and validate the risk guide and the security black box testing methodology presented as part of the security recommendations. Overall, this document describes a full process for secure integration of digital solutions within water utilities.

On the training side, the work performed in STOP-IT, has been extended in DWC. Here, D4.8⁴ presents material for a training scheme on cyber-physical security for water network operators.

The training material comprises the following modules:

- Course Introduction – introduction to CP security
- Water systems as cyber-physical entities
- Information Systems for water
- Communication technologies for water
- Risk Management for Cyber-physical Security
- IoT Security for water systems
- Organizational Resilience Training

The STOP-IT risk management process as integrated approach cyber-physical

Protecting water infrastructure against cyber and physical threats is the main objective of the STOP-IT project. One of the key messages, we have delivered with STOP-IT to the operators, is that more resilient water services are not achieved just by protecting the infrastructure against cyber or physical threats, but by adopting an integrated approach that combines the cyber (IT and SCADA) and the physical layers (the networks and related assets) of the water systems both at strategic/tactical and operational level; this approach should also, in an interactive and integrated approach, assess and treat the cascading effects of threats from one to the other layer.

A guide aligned with this message and aiming at supporting the water sector in performing integrated risk management has been produced in the DWC project. The guide relates to the more generic risk management standard ISO 31000:2018 in order to ensure more flexibility of the presented approach when adopted by water utilities, independently to the standards or guidelines to which their risk management plans are grounded to (e.g., water safety and security plans).

Furthermore, the scenario-based stress-testing approaches proposed in the guide from DWC and supported by the platforms developed in STOP-IT could also serve as inspirational example for critical entities operators in the process of implementing the upcoming CER directives.

Willingness to share

To support the need of information exchange among utilities and critical infrastructure operators in general, STOP-IT has designed and implemented a Cyber Threat Sharing System, collecting sources of existing threats from relevant feeds, and structuring the information using standards to facilitate the exchange of the security threats identified (e.g. MITRE, OASIS). Personalized alerts and relevant

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/7998642>

information can be provided according to the subscription parameters requested by a given critical infrastructure sector. This service helps operators affected by the cyber incidents to increase the level of preparedness by communicating incidents alerts, it also enhances the coordination within sectors in establishing exchange methods to prevent, reduce, mitigate and recover from existing threats and it could allow the coordination actions to deal with critical infrastructure threats in a global approach at National level.

Furthermore, we would like to underline the need for effective cybersecurity information sharing between the various essential entities in Europe, including private entities of all sectors. Cybersecurity has a horizontal applicability to organisations of all sectors, therefore private-private cooperation should be encouraged, and more ways should be explored to build trust among different private entities in the context of information sharing. Private entities in the water sector should be able to utilise these information sharing channels not only within the water sector but also horizontally across different sectors, as cybersecurity threats are of a transversal nature. Therefore, an idea would be the engagement of actors of different sectors at an **EU-wide platform on information-sharing** including all types of water sector related entities (being private, public, semi-private or semi-public).

Training activities and awareness creation

Water utilities and national or local governance bodies and stakeholders linked to the utilities, need to have a better understanding on potential cybersecurity threats and best practices when it comes to dealing with such threats. Therefore, it is important to effectively raise awareness on both physical and digital security risks at an EU-wide level and thus invest on the training of the relevant staff working in essential sectors such as the ones of water utilities. Experiences from the STOP-IT project and the knowledge of various EU-wide partners can be used to scale up the training material developed so to be used for raising awareness or even training purposes.

This process is established as a spin-off of the project through the establishment of an EU Water ISAC. The STOP-IT coordination team, although the project ended, is still engaged in forming the core of a successful European Water ISAC, building upon the results of STOP-IT and DWC and gathering water operators, the industrial sector and the research community willing to contribute in creating the most valuable source for water and wastewater situational awareness. The EU Water ISAC should provide in-depth water safety and security information not yet available for most European water utilities.

Checklist for IoT security

In the DWC project, we have analyzed the risks potentially brought by the adoption of the digital solutions developed as part of the project and derived a high-level classification of attacks against them⁵. As the IoT-related risks were a blind spot during our conversations with water utilities, we performed a security assessment on a typical IoT-based solution, in order to raise awareness about these risks. We show that while the solutions might not be directly connected with the water utilities' systems, they pose a risk for supply chain attacks and/or can be misused to lead to incorrect decisions being made.

⁵ <https://www.mdpi.com/2624-800X/3/1/6>

Based on our experience, we concluded that knowledge of cyber security varies significantly among actors in the water sector. SINTEF has collected experiences from several European and national projects, and created an IoT security checklist⁶ that a vendor or water network operator can use to ensure a minimum level of security in a given solution.

References

- [1] This text is reproduced from U. Cali et al.: "Cyber-physical Hardening of the Digital Water Infrastructure", EICC 2023
- [2] Reference: Umit Cali, Ferhat Ozgur Catak, Zsolt György Balogh, Rita Ugarelli, and Martin Gilje Jaatun. 2023. Cyber-physical Hardening of the Digital Water Infrastructure. In European Interdisciplinary Cybersecurity Conference (EICC 2023), June 14–15, 2023, Stavanger, Norway. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 8 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3590777.3591408>
- [3] Chapters 6, in John Soldatos (ed.), Isabel Praça (ed.), Aleksandar Jovanović (ed.) (2021), "Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence for Critical Infrastructures Security: Securing Critical Infrastructures in Air Transport, Water, Gas, Healthcare, Finance and Industry", Boston-Delft: now publishers, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1561/9781680838237>

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⁶ <https://www.sintef.no/contentassets/8fa5c7e3a81749b8952979000ee34c31/iot-security-checklist-v1.1.0.pdf>

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